

Novel Biomarkers in Histopathology: Implications for Diagnosis and Prognosis

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Abstract

Identification of new biomarkers in histopathology for better understanding of disease diagnosis and outcome has received interest. Significant progresses have been achieved in these fronts in cancer diagnosis through biomarkers in different tumors including Ki-67. Ki-67 is a biomarker that is used to support its diagnostic and prognostic cost showing potential in diseases like gliomas, meningiomas, medulloblastomas, and ependymomas. HER2 is overexpressed for the diagnosis and predictability of breast cancer, while MSMB and PSG2 are ideal biomarkers for prostate adenocarcinoma. Cancer has dominated most of the study conducted within this field, therefore it is important for the research to go on and apply these new biomarkers in clinical facilities for enhancement in diagnosis and prediction of other diseases. It is noteworthy that other directions, for instance therapeutic response, reveal a considerable rise in comparison with the indicators of the last year. Some of the new biomarkers require additional new complex and costly technology, but the researchers agree that these discoveries and practising the new biomarkers should help clinicians make a better decision depending on the correct assessment of the patient's state. Moreover, many biomarkers still need confirming in the samples used as examinations. Today, new biomarkers that are applied to cancer diagnostics are based on the availability of simple samples including sweat, urine, blood, cerebrospinal fluid, and saliva. It is important to increase the use of such samples since obtaining them is easy, and the subject can be sampled with little or no interferences at all in terms of invasiveness. The convenience not only increases the willingness of the patient in compliance to the diagnostic process, but also delivers a far enhanced healthcare experience and results. Therefore, with the help of the biomarkers presented earlier and implementing them together with other innovative state of the art techniques for detection and identification, the process has been revolutionized. They possess remarkable features that are essential owing to the fact that biomarker molecules that cannot be identified by routine assessment modalities because of structural or molecular weight differences are well highlighted. In other words, these techniques have provided a first-of-its-kind approach to recognising and identifying innovative evaluation and analysis techniques for biomarkers. However, it is imperative that such strategies come with related costs and expenses in order to be executed. However, relying on the mentioned considerations, mass spectrometry is invariably recognized as probably the most advisable and definitely the preferred option to implement in laboratories or commercial as well as medical facilities. Over all while the cost implication of mass spectrometry

More Information

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are somewhat high they are offset by the advantages of high accuracy, sensitivity and specificity of the technique. It has evolved as a critical asset for biomarker analysis and clinical use, which in the long run results in better prognosis of cancer and precise therapy intercession. They add that the ongoing upgrade and enhancement of mass spectrometry technologies produce new advances in biomarker analysis, thus maintaining mass spectrometry as the focus of the biomarker.

Introduction to Histopathology and Biomarkers

In pathologic practice, histopathology as a scientific method is defined as a process of investigating diseases at the tissue level. Pathologist actually diagnose tissues and cells to deduce nature and characteristics of tissue and cellular disease. The technique of histopathological examination has remained almost the same, but the scientific data that the pathologist requires in coming to a diagnosis have altered. A biomarker is a biological marker that makes it possible to distinguish one phenotype from another. In histopathology, extrapolations of molecular and genetic nature are making histopathology a more accurate process. Today with so many advanced treatment options including use of drugs in patients it is the biomarker that assists in the use of the modern approach to treatment –which is the personalized medicine [1,2].

Therefore, biomarkers take an important position whenever it comes towards the notion of early and accurate diagnosis of different diseases. In medical situations, it is greatly implied by use and recommendation which biomarkers may occasionally require for management plan. The drafted guidelines for the management teams, in many scenarios elaborate on the status of key biomarkers from diverse boards at the international level such as, oncology. Also, diagnostic confirmation as well as prognosis in different diverse boards for experts and pathologists is significant. A marker that has function in prognosis direction or a prediction marker may perform the decision important in treatment. It can be in choosing correct agents to be used in the frame work of various treatment plans or in excluding possible toxic agents to boot. In the clinical application of some biomarkers, its status of the individual qualities and response to the treatment. It is now understood that pathologists are, in fact, arriving at a diagnosis at multiple tiers, yet one of the methodologies created based on morphological distribution throughout the body is assessing at multiple tiers, although each tier has different probabilities of prediction. Pathology is choosing an action that will be crystallized in the future pattern of behavior, with an eye to the likely outcome in a man with a given proclivity [3,4].

Histopathology Definition

Histopathology is one way of examining tissues especially examining them under CLOSED_ microscopes in order to display characteristics of diseases. It is the examination of biological tissue by means of a histological diagnosis performed under the

aid of a visual light and electron microscope. In particular, in diagnosis, the histopathologist has to link the findings apparent during microscopy to clinical, radiological, or other tests. The rationale of biopsy and/or other parts of the patients is to enable the histopathologist to categorize the tissue as normal/benign or abnormal/malignant, to what degree [5].

Histopathology is a matter of significant context in clinical medicine. There is a prediction that about 70 per cent of the health care decisions that may influence the diagnosis or the treatment process involve the use of a pathology service. Daily, millions of samples of blood, urine, feces and tissue specimens are processed and tested in the laboratory. Modern histopathology is a boon in that at no time in the entire history of pathology can as much access to information be gained. During the reign of Queen Victoria, in response to a histological inquiry in regard to the state of a patient, there was but one figure given – the figure of survival over sundry intervals of time: “ alive 18 hours subsequent to the operation.” Today we can obtain millions of mostly molecular data that will help not only in diagnosis but also in prognosis, in selection of the therapy type, as well as in the assessment of the efficiency of the therapy [6].

The microscopy techniques in tissues have been in practice for over 150 years using the light microscopes and over 70 years of electron microscope. At that time, the exposure of a specific protein could more clearly distinguish the cell type present within a tumor. While these methods may be limited by technology, as the latter progresses, so does the investigation of cells. The specific techniques applied were inexpensive and uncomplicated to execute, therefore, less complicated in their interpretation partly due to knowledge acquired. It is, therefore, not surprising that technical developments in histopathology have been slow in embracing WSI, maybe being surpassed by innovation rather than driving it. One field that has grown and completely depends on tissue material from the pathologist is histopathology with biomarkers. Tissue is still very much needed for histomorphology, or for what is relatively new on our list, nucleic acid test for tumor assessment. Biopsy has its roots from the early fifth century when there was a technique in which pus from ulcers was removed for diagnostic purposes noted [7,8].

Role of Biomarkers in Disease Diagnosis and Prognosis

Biomarkers are residues or quantifiable molecular signs of biological events, including gene activity, protein synthesis, cellular activity and behavior, or even many others. Blood, tissues, and body fluids are the conveyors of these indicators; when there is a pathological condition, the concentration or structure of an item changes and emerges or is absent, or is present at a low or high level. There are diverse definitions regarding biomarkers that have been provided in the literature. The most often cited definition is "A trait that is quantifiable and assessed in respect to a reference point of normal physiological functioning, a disease, or a response to a treatment." Biomarkers are uniquely capable to diagnose distinct diseases (diagnostic biomarker) and possibly even their expected progression (prognostic biomarker) or how a patient will respond to a new or current treatment regimen (predictive biomarker). There are of different forms; diagnostic biomarkers are early indications of a disease that may not exhibit any resultant clinical manifestations; prognostic biomarkers state the possibility of histology, grade, stage, as well as aggressiveness of the disease; and the last one is a predictive biomarker, which identifies types of cancers, and, in particular, the results of responsive different treatment procedures.

Thus, only accurate and validated biomarkers are the need of the present and, particularly, the future. It is made clear that diseases can have definite symptoms in different people and diagnostic and prognostic possibilities give the overall and patient-specific vision of the problem. The future of clinical practice will be an Integrated Omics Machine Learning Medical Science that documents changes and evaluates all diseases as real patient experiences do, set priorities, and determine the best approach. This means it does take personalised medicine to a level of reinventing medicine as well as greatly assisting individual therapy. Even though there were certain concerns about examining different omics, advances made in the last four decades regarding imaging biomarkers, which also focused on different omics, constitute overwhelming evidence and their discovery, validation and acceptance changed clinical medicine and surgery for the better by adding value and increasing importance and applicability in numerous widespread disorders to which biomarkers can be constantly subjected to aid society in overcoming issues such as population ageing and the skyrocketing incidence of chronic disorders which

Traditional Biomarkers in Histopathology

Through the years, numerous routine staining morphology in histopathology had been tried and some discovered to be beneficial in diagnostics and prognostics. These classical biomarkers are useful to

physicians for diagnosing an illness and also for evaluating the response to therapy in practice. The proteins that are chosen as being characteristic of some pathological state change in concentration in the body fluids or tissues. Tissues or cells which are damaged secrete enzymes in blood stream or body fluids; hence, variations in any enzyme can contain valuable diagnostic or prognostic significance during diseases. For example, carcinoembryonic antigens are biomolecules that have found application in several clinical disciplines including oncology. These antigens are a soluble glycoprotein existing in the epithelial cells of a fetus liver. Patients with cancer are proved to have higher levels. Higher levels can give other factors that may indicate 'minimal residual disease.' This frequently results in re-disease for a number of reasons [13,14].

The research of traditional biomarkers has become the first step in increments and has recently entered the stage of stagnation. These traditional tissue biomarkers of the structural changes in the tissue and the cellular damages have been useful not only in diagnostic techniques but also in making prognosis. However, traditional biomarkers also has some drawbacks. For some pathologies, the biomarkers which have been used so far are not sufficiently sensitive and specific. As in most pathological tests, including histopathological tests, which are routine, many of the pathologies are very difficult to detect and pinpoint. Casting thus new trends in molecular medicine, and histological technology, have emerged as the major research interests. The familiar search for new biomarkers has also become the care of many researchers. Consequently, traditional biomarkers are a starting point of studying new diagnostics and can be considered as development of research in the field [15,16].

Commonly Used Biomarkers in Clinical Practice

Current clinical applications have a number of classical biomarkers that distinguish them from others. Of the commonly used biomarkers which include alpha-fetoprotein, carcinoembryonic antigen, cancer antigen 125, cancer antigen 15-3, prostate-specific antigen and beta-human chorionic gonadotropin are some of the biomarkers which were included in the materials. These biomarkers improve the ability of diagnosing cancer with a high degree of accuracy. Also all these biomarkers correspond to specific types of cancer, and I consider that there is correlation between all of them. AFP has some utility in diagnosing HCC in chronic liver diseases and is also an independent predictor of prognosis in HCC. Carcinoembryonic antigen is also applied to other forms of cancer and is most frequently associated with colon cancer. There is evidence of CA 125 for comparing the prognosis of patients with epithelial ovarian cancer and for diagnosing early ovarian cancer and evaluating the efficacy of the

therapy. Cancer antigen 15-3 is another cancer markers well used in patients with advanced breast cancer. People diagnosed of prostate cancer have their prostate specific antigen levels checked to determine their disease status. Beta-human chorionic gonadotropin is commercially relevant for diagnosing germ cell cancer, more so in seminoma cancer [17,18]. This paper aims at exploring the importance of histopathology in diagnosing some of the diseases. In most diseases patients treatment depends on histopathological reports for the reason that biopsy reports give a lot of information regarding the structure of the tissue sample. There are several nosological forms of diseases in which biopsy reports act as the alpha and omega of treatment. For these reasons, no other diagnostic investigation could be used in place of the biopsy for diagnosis. In addition, in some diseases, biopsy holds a great potential that help in making correct diagnosis of cases that might be complicated. Treatments, chemotherapists, and hormonal therapists are often determined by the biopsy report many a time. The present circulatory tissue biomarkers include alpha-fetoprotein, carcinoembryonic antigen, cancer antigen 15-3, cancer antigen 125, alongside Cancer antigen 19-9 and have cone-like significances for enhancing the prognosis for long-term treatment and early diagnosis of diseases. It is also useful in design of new remedial trials for biomarkers These biomarkers are also useful in creating new remedial trials. In addition to the detection of diseases on the initial stages and prognosis of the disease, these marker systems are invaluable in usual practice for determining further therapy and follow-up of the patient. However, the action of these biomarkers is presupposed by the need for proper treatment in one case, interpreting the level of the biomarkers and their patterns in each case of the diseases. More often than not, the measurement or interpretation of one household biomarker in a household will not be complete from a single test. In some cancers it is not any absolute value of a certain marker or any of the combination among them that improve the diagnosis of the disease. In achieving the biomarkers' result, details to assess in histopathology laboratory reports include features such as staining intensity or a grading system. They are also discussed in this paper, as happen in the abovementioned issues, which represent a future challenge [19,20].

Emerging Biomarkers in Histopathology

As per the definition accepted now, biomarker is defined it is an characteristic that is measured and recorded with normal biological processes or pathology, or with response to treatment. Biomarkers are essential tools used in epidemiologic research providing clear quantitative information. As formulated initially to pertain to intrinsic systematic impacts on cells or tissues, the notion of a biomarker

was gradually stretched to the point where today it can embrace information as its subject matter. The latter shows that at present, the advancement of technology in any given field creates new subfields of study or the identification of new biological attributes that require biomarkers. In fact, an increased interest in the concept of tumor heterogeneity subsequently resulted in the identification of genetic and epigenetic changes activated in subclones of tumor cells. Hence, these novel biomarkers can capture the genetic heterogeneity and functional diversity of attributable individual tumors more informatively than a bulk mass evaluation. The clinical research interest of such concepts has aimed at identifying the appearance of treatment-resistant or pro-metastatic cellular clones or cancer stem cells out of the overall tumour mass. From continued studies and consequent findings, several of these new biomarkers may potentially shift the histopathology-driven cancer diagnostic parameters in humans by substantial percentage. For example, over the past few years there has been a growing amount of data about the phenotypic transdifferentiation of benign stromal cells surrounding carcinoma cells into CAFs by protein expression during the last years. Biological reasons for the diagnostic usefulness of these fibroblasts are centred mostly on the viewpoint of the ability of carcinoma cells to reprogram adjacent cells, including fibroblasts into cancer-related phenotypes [21,22].

Novel Biomarkers in Cancer Diagnosis

More specifically, multiple molecular markers have recently been identified in cancer research in the early years of the third millennium that might enhance the diagnosis of neoplastic diseases. Human scientists distinguish some of these markers as breakthroughs because of their measurability and selectivity. Therefore, they provide the opportunity to establish an early diagnosis and effective treatment for each subject. However, many of these novel markers have now been identified due to research conducted on an international level of basic research and multimodal approaches. Such examples include the N-terminally truncated peptides of cytokeratin-18 and identification of the protein called γ H2AX for prediction of neoplasia. Moreover, some of the novel potential markers indicate initial intracellular changes in tumor formation. For instance, the human protein Wilms' tumor 1 (WT1) is a transcription factor that may be used to evaluate the likelihood of cancer patient's response to chemotherapy. Perhaps another promising candidate, cytokeratin-20 (K20) mRNA, is with carcinomatous meningitis in breast cancer and may be significant to novel therapeutic targets [23-25].

The biomarker WT1 is applied in the differential diagnosis algorithm in children with steroid-resistant nephrotic syndrome to diagnose nephroblastoma.

Furthermore, an OverExpress molecule has been employed for validation of the Human CEACAM6 tumor marker in peripheral blood as a diagnostic marker in colon cancer. These novel potential markers can enhance diagnosis and management of patients with solid cancers and hematologic malignancies. A number of investigations have been performed to corroborate the significance of multiple protein and nucleic acid biomarkers in neoplastic diseases. Among these markers some of them has been undoubtedly identified belong to breast, ovarian, lung, colon and prostate cancer. Having reviewed a number of publications, the authors now talk about the prospect of actual diagnostic and therapeutic strategy linking novel tumor biomarkers to molecular markers of tumorigenesis. A part of the novel markers have been used to diagnosing the disease and some of them have been patented. The possibilities of using these markers in clinical practice and the ways through which many of the abovementioned markers exert their effect are highlighted. And, once again, it is important to note that one of the most complex tasks in contemporary medicine is the integration of new markers with advanced, efficient, effective, and highly resolution diagnostics. Silencing or reduced levels of expression of the WT1 gene has also been found to cause growth inhibition and or apoptosis in numerous lines of malignant tumor cells without having appreciable effect on normal cells [26-28].

Technological Advances in Biomarker Detection

Progress in technology has wholly overhauled biomarker identification techniques from being imprudent dyes in early biochemistry to accurate detection procedures in current anatomic pathology. That dynamic has sharply advanced the hunt for new biomarkers to detect because it means for the first time, researchers can now identify proteins that could perhaps serve as improved biomarkers. Examples of these include DNA or RNA or microRNA assays, proteomics, multiplex immunoassays involving the use of standardized antibodies or immunohistochemistry with specific and sensitive antibodies [35,36]. Techniques in the histopathological laboratories have not previously been investigated in step by step validation studies because of their specific and specialized conditions of operations. new and improved biomarkers. This can be accomplished using various cutting-edge techniques such as DNA/RNA or microRNA assays, proteomics, multiplex immunoassays with standardized antibodies, or immunohistochemistry with highly specific and sensitive antibodies [35,36]. Laboratory techniques in the field of histopathology have, until now, rarely been the subject of detailed validation studies due to their specific and unique settings and working practices. Nonetheless, with the development of technology we

have been able to identify biomarkers at the cellular level, for instance, proteins exercising special activity or proteins that participate in certain critical pathways. In anatomic pathology there is now possibility to detect RNA and DNA mutations in cancer samples that significantly improve ability to predict response to targeted therapy [29,30]. Highly specific and sensitive detection methods in modern anatomic pathology. These groundbreaking innovations have significantly accelerated the search for new biomarkers to detect because we are currently able to identify proteins that could potentially serve as new and improved biomarkers. This can be accomplished using various cutting-edge techniques such as DNA/RNA or microRNA assays, proteomics, multiplex immunoassays with standardized antibodies, or immunohistochemistry with highly specific and sensitive antibodies [35,36]. Laboratory techniques in the field of histopathology have, until now, rarely been the subject of detailed validation studies due to their specific and unique settings and working practices. However, with the recent advancements in technology, we have been able to detect biomarkers at the cellular level, such as proteins with special functions or those involved in essential pathways. In anatomic pathology, we can now detect RNA and DNA mutations in cancer samples, which greatly facilitates the prediction of response to targeted therapies [29,30]. Furthermore, we have broadened the array of our competence since we have exposed the tumour in ascites of diverse histologic source, for identification of growth factors, growth factor receptors, signaling molecules, transcription factors, and effector as well as protectants. This multifaceted approach would enable the researchers to get broad insights about the different aetiologies of different diseases. This is especially important in immunohistochemistry practice where antibodies are extremely useful and mandatory for the elimination of false positive staining. That the method is 'user friendly' or more to the point cost effective is now equally important as is the assurance that a technique or procedure is sensitive or specific. Creating a perfect harmony of these aspects, we can expand the opportunities for increasing the effectiveness of biomarker detection and fight for the progress of biomedical science and healthcare industry. In conclusion, due to the tremendous advances in technology, biomarker detection has gone through a revolution from less specific technique to a more sensitive and specific one. These advancements have made it possible in addition to helping identify new biomarkers also to gain insights into diseases and their causes. As we progress in enhancing some laboratory process particularly in histopathology, the dissemination of these methods together with the validation will pave way to the enhancement in the field

of histopathology for the benefit of both researchers and patients in the future [31,32]. However, to facilitate this process of validating new biomarkers it is vital that proteins, RNA/DNA mutations, polymorphisms or transcription factors are accurately detected by histopathology methods because immunohistochemistry, in situ hybridization, tissue microarrays, next-generation sequencing, chromatin immunoprecipitation sequencing, methylated DNA assays, and RNA sequencing technologies have made a pivotal and ancillary contribution towards the discovery of new biomarkers with progn. With these discovery, it is currently feasible to describe a 'multi-gene' strategy of targeting additional genes or proteins in an effort to strive for the development of novel 'personalized medicine' biomarker panels which may lead to better patient titration and more effective clinical trial conception and results. The new and, as a rule, highly sensitive methods are likely to take the place of the older ones because the required amounts of specimens are considerably smaller. However, equal one of the most frequent points of concern for immunohistochemical analysis is the highly subjective nature of the results interpretation due to the problems with the antibodies standardization and validation. Some shortcomings of the various technologies are described, and the necessity for additional validation studies is also identified. Such biomarker, as indicated, would serve as the definitive diagnostic tool, a tool to track disease progression and response to treatment, although, for biomedical and clinical advancement the simultaneous, extensive, prospective, and qualitative analysis of these proliferative agents is evident if we obtain a comprehensive panel of molecules in multi-target fashion for individualized medicine [33,34].

Immunohistochemistry

IHC is one of the basic techniques for visualizing antigens in tissue sections, here the use of antibodies to point out the location of particular antigens in cells and tissues. It supplies data on the distribution and density of antigens and is suitable not only for paraffin-embedded tissues but also for frozen sections and smear smears. In diagnostic histopathology of invasive cancers especially those with phenotypic heterogeneity, IHC is useful in predicting significant clinical behavior, prognosis or response to treatment. When a good diagnostic IHC panel is preset, clinicians might take advantage of shorter duration for diagnostic endeavor and better, more frequently less intrusive, forms of treatment. Using IHC and molecular biology approaches have enabled new potential biomarker for characterization of target diseases [35-37].

Some of these disease-specific studies describe diseases related to the immune response and to tumor processes. At present, IHC is more and more to

recognize new potential biomarkers for expression, tumor in situ surrounding tissues, nodal spread, tumor recurrence, therapy impact on tumors or tumor environment, prognosis or predictive effects on oncological and non – oncological diseases. IHC is an invasive method, but in the present time it has not been standardized well and is low on reproducibility and sensitivity main especially for low copy mRNAs or surface-antigens. Using IHC methodology is undergoes continual technological enhancement and therefore IHC may be more sensitive and has been used when detecting circulating free tumor antigens. That these new circulating and free antigen biomarkers are being studied for behavior and prognosis have attracted considerable interest in clinical and basic investigations. IHC is a gold standard in clinical practice, not only for diagnostic but also for prognostic or predictive purposes: The discussion is centered on the estimating use of IHC in diagnostic subtyping and classifying solid cancers and in defining expression of disease markers for treatment strategy. IHC has the following advantages in diagnostic research. IHC can depict the correct anatomic distribution of the antigen in disease or pathological tissue and in occasional situations could represent the sole strategy to do so because of its use in immunostaining cytologic preparations. In the summary of the IHC features below: – IHC is useful to determine the anatomical distribution of a molecule – IHC is useful to semiquantitate a gene – Modern IHC maybe normalized to quantitate – IHC can detect changes of the cell membrane in the form of vesiculation – IHC can be used to expand phenotyping panels by presetting the differential diagnosis.

Fluorescence In Situ Hybridization (FISH)

Among the considered technologies it emerges that FISH can be used for visualizing and detecting the cellular features associated with cancer which can be considered as biomarkers. Since its development more than thirty years ago, FISH has proved to be a highly delicate method for identifying a particular DNA or RNA in cells of a tissue section. There are many commercial FISH systems that enable pathologists to detect and map DNA loci on a given chromosome or gene expression which is amplified, translocated, deleted, or mutated. The method being commonly used in the diagnostic stage that relates to cancer. Studies of various and more specific tumor types in several trials both ongoing and completed have aimed at defining the potential of FISH [42,43].

In the case of tissue biopsy, the FISH technology was employed to study the cell heterogeneity and the imprinting of tissue sample in terms of feature or cell types successively found within a sample. Furthermore, multiple signals per outcome strategies are appropriate as second-generation companion diagnostic tools to be

used with the pharmaceutical products. One major drawback has been how sophisticated it is to interpret and the level of experience the outcome and formulation of a diagnosis on a sample. The FISH Cell Application has grown to embrace and even value these disease indicators, or biomarkers as they are recognised today. However, to kick-start fundamental research with biomarkers, a reliance on technologies has previously been made and it is seen that these technologies are not stagnant themselves [44-46].

Biomarker studies have used FISH to detect chromosomal arrangements and gene fusions and it can be expected that in the future advances in FISH approaches—effective detection for example somatic mutations, larger amplicons or genomic rearrangements—will be able to detect other predefined alterations that drive cancers. FISH was in fact utilized as the go to approach to co-localize IHC versions of PD-L1 to cancer cells in metastatic NSCLC, UC and more recently SCC H&N.

Challenges and Limitations in Biomarker Research

There are several obstacles and constraints associated with biomarkers development during the biomarkers development process. The process is not linear and mostly consists of several steps; therefore, biomarker development is complex and multifaceted. The creation of Biomarker tests takes a long time in development, and we typically encounter a temporal gap of multiple years from the time the histological study identifies a new potential marker to the time a readily usable test is available in a clinical setting. In part, this protracted timeframe is owing to the absence of effective communication links between pathologists operating in this area, basic researchers who develop or validate new biomarkers, and clinical practitioners who consult with patients. As a result, there are some deficiencies in communication that hamper the biomarkers' further development and unsuccessfully translate grounded research into practice to provide better health care services [50,51].

Heterogeneity is again a major issue with regards to all forms of biomarker expression assessed for histology, as well as the molecular diagnostics assays. The benefits of different characteristics of tumors are understandable, however there is a problem in heterogeneity and it is both opportunity in a sphere of fundamental investigations and the possible shortage in its further usage at clinics level. In general, it is possible to state that at the organism level a highly significant variability regarding the expression of antigens in tissues is characteristic and, therefore, issues of reproducibility of the obtained results, including in subsequent research, and, in general, the possibilities of using these antigens as disease markers, whether in the context of diagnostics or exerting assessment on the impact of the applied therapy, may

be rather restrained. Besides comparative epidemiological investigations using stored tissue and distinct high-throughput data, major diagnostic clinical trials are required for biomarker assessment. A certain degree of dissimilarity in terms of the methodological approaches or generally utilized protocols for validation and methods for evaluation may restrain the utility of these studies and is mentioned as one of the main problems in biomarker validation. Ethical consideration have been on a rise in the biomedical research for the last decades. The acquiring and application of clinical and socio-demographic information collected from persons when enrolled in a treatment or interventional study for purposes of registering disease has become a routine in majority of medical research programs. However, the data such as this, or simply tissue specimens collected for tests can lead to a number of ethical concerns. Patient related data or data of any groups of people may be different from country to country regarding the genetic data of people. Of these, Anonymity in the use of tissue or related data has become critical, and appropriate legislation and the matching official code has been made in most of societies. It is therefore relevant and necessity of society to use such data and specimens in accordance to ethical standards. However, the potential to share such data and the potential to use archival tissue or biological material samples for the actual registration of the burden of development some diseases it is needed that society is ready to accept it. Sharing this resource requires working together with patient organisations as well as public authorities and politicians in order to enable the latter to make optimum and sustainable use of the full potential value offered by the resource. Hence, databases established should have most probably been secured and financed over a long period and will call for great efforts in putting in place the right codification and storage of the safe specimen tracking and against other forms of access by unauthorized persons. A mutually shared personal scientific Identity will then also guarantee that projects pertaining such ALS related tissue specimens can be conducted on a transnational basis. Altogether, such studies not only provide a generally more proof-based kind of research but also lead to higher possibilities of identifying diagnoses and the effects of potential new disease types. Moreover, they provide authors with a potential basis for publishing data in highly ranked journals. Increased effort is required for the validation of other possibly new promising biomarkers in cooperation between basic scientists or epidemiologists and clinicians in order to minimise these limitations [52-55]. It also further underscores the relevance of heterogeneity for biomarker expression in relation to segmenting the market. There are growing difficulties affecting both the fundamental

research and the clinical utility as a result of this issue. Although there are evident advantages of defining various characteristics of tumors, there are challenges that need to be met. The antigens expression in tissues is highly heterogeneous, which may bring difficulties to experimental replication and expand the clinical application of these antigens as diagnostic and therapeutic biomarkers. Thus, together with comparative epidemiological studies and high-throughput data analysis, large diagnostic, clinical trials should be also performed for effective biomarkers' assessment. In this regard, a major drawback in biomarkers validation processes is the absence of a uniformity of the methodological possibilities and the protocols for validation/evaluation [56,57]. During the past few decades, ethics relevant to biomedical research have changed dramatically. It has also become standard in medical research programs to incorporate clinical data and the socio demographics of people who participate in treatment or in interventional studies. However, there is a wide range of ethical concern when such data is used or when collected tissue specimens are used. Since patient-related data or may be sensitive data, there may be certain differences between countries as far as policies and laws for the use of such data and more specifically data concerning genetics are concerned. To conceal tissue identity and usage of data, the requirement of proper legislation and official policy has emerged in most societies. It is right and requisite as a social responsibility to employ such data and specimens in an excellent manner. Disease progression knowledge sharing entails data sharing using body tissues or biological material specimen receipts archived with another party. To facilitate effective utilisation of such shared resources, it is important to form strong partnerships with patient organisation, public institutions and policymakers. It is important to do the following in the form of appropriation and security: It takes time to develop safe and adequately funded databases to provide proper and correct labeling of specimens as well as protection from intruders. This will help make interdisciplinary, transnational cooperative projects easier that, for instance, involve the exchange of tissue samples, as well as supporting the establishment of research based on empirical data, diagnostic tools, and potentially newly defined diseases. In addition, it will provide a good ground on which authors can be able to upload their data to high impact journals. In order to minimize limitations associated with methodological heterogeneity, albeit objectively acknowledging the potential of the approach, further attempts at validating potentially valuable biomarkers need to be undertaken. This could be done through integration between basic researchers, disease servers, and clinical officers. They can independently perform such tasks as

closing gaps and transferring the necessary information as well as introducing new diagnostic methods that will undoubtedly improve the outcome for patients [59-62].

Heterogeneity in Biomarker Expression

Biomarker expression is not necessarily continuous, and patients present with high signal, low signal, and no signal at all. Such a distribution is called heterogeneity or, in terms of biomarkers mapping, the geographic manifestation of biomarkers, and can be regarded as one of the primary issues in this kind of studies. It is also true that area selection for biopsies can influence such results, which is why initial studies on these biomarkers will give a number of names which are sometimes contradictory, either because the results are not reproducible, or because of patient selection. The fact is that the concept is based only on the study of the cancer disease itself in the individual patient's case. Second, tumor heterogeneity is instrumental for the continued existence of medicine, and this knowledge is what creates prognostic and predictive biomarkers. When using these data for your study, do not choose the patients to include, arbitrarily. This is because, as in clinical practice, patient variability regarding the biomarker must be taken into account to achieve valuable findings [63,64].

To address current difficulties associated with analysis and histopathology of tumor heterogeneity based on the spatial and copied event, it is recommended to be rather cautious in clinical applications according to guidelines of current investigators, as their patients receive a certain course of targeted agents stained with fluorescent in situ biomarkers. Owing to the heterogeneity of the expression profile in a single individual, it would therefore appear that a target-based assay without an additional diagnostic stage for the generation of prognostic biomarkers could not, in the main, forecast a patient's response to targeted treatment. However, this can already be considered as a potential problem that the researcher can easily foresee and that is why, it is more effective to come up with more specific panels for the diagnostic assays. This panel should also be developed for random trials particularly those in the early phases. More work that classifies patient characteristics based on the presided molecular expression and the physical interpretation of the tumor microenvironment is required in the future. The MATH value could therefore be lowered provided that accurate automated lymphocyte counting and positivity for collagen and PDPN would be considered to make particular subtypes of tumor heterogeneity feasible for the panel. Probably these tools could also be extended into the practice of clinical medicine to advance the specifics of therapeutic approaches. Further investigations are also required to indentify the reduced predictive capacity or the enhancement of survival from biopsy.

Clinical Applications of Novel Biomarkers

As the use of biomarker advances to disease management, it gains advantages in diagnostic evaluations, therapeutics, and a potential future application to trial and drug studies. One of the most important tasks of oncologists in clinical practice is to determine what individual treatment options might be optimal for a particular patient based on the molecular characteristics of his or her cancer. Nevertheless, relying only on histomorphology to reach the definitive diagnosis does not provide enough information to guide patient management anymore. Of the changes in the neoplastic cells more recently the genomic ones, the transcriptomic ones, and the proteomic ones are designed for the reorganisation of alterations in the genome of malignant cells, definition of new targets for medications, which is applied in routine clinical practice owing to the identification of new biomarkers and can give focus on theranostic data. For instance, a 70-y-old man who ever smoked cannot receive immunotherapy unless some powerful biomarkers for predicting the likelihood of success are found, though he is surely something like immunotherapy [67,68].

In other words, the key components of clinical assessment of any diagnostic test can be seen as important as the magnitude of the benefit and cost and risk associated with it. In the context of molecular tests, this is further a function of the scale of ancillary costs including the trainer's or pathologist's hourly salary, solution costs, reagents, kits, slides, and control blocks for immunohistochemistry, and should, therefore, include the upfront capital costs of ancillary equipment or the rental charges in addition to the labor time required for post-staining care. These will usually be less formidable in most but not all diagnostic settings than for expensive molecular assays or developable biomarkers. As for the short-term vision of these novel biomarkers, they will act only as signal amplifiers indicating diagnostically significant spheres for further exhaustive, sequential micro-morphometric and cellular-molecular diagnostic technologies with on-chip microfluidics for highly-sensitive, selective molecular assessment. In addition, employing of these lesser expensive biomarkers as a rule may level up semiquantitative visual dissimilarities between various areas assessment can be given on a daily basis [69-70].

Precision Medicine Approaches

The area involved in oncology at the present time is involved in a rather intricate but viable setting known as the precision medicine. This very challenging area of advancement is focused on offering differentiated alterations to current and emergent therapies based on patients' characteristics. It is a strategy that accommodates variation on the traditional method of diagnosing, managing and preventing disease through availing the genetic factors of the disease.

Consequently, biomarkers play the critical role in the concept of PM and have been under intensive investigation. Not only are they diagnostic of diseases in a more accurate manner than clinical or histological analysis but they also indicate the molecular basis of diseases and molecular signatures linked directly to their therapeutic targets. However, the pairing of a biomarker with the right targeted treatment is a revolutionary approach to dealing with advanced as well as metastasized cancers [71,72].

But, there are certain limitations encountered in translating an effective concept of precision medicine being accepted by actual clinical practice. There are validity issues as a result of issues relating to integration of testing modalities, challenges, and expenses in both the developed nations and low-infrastructure middle income. Precision medicine has defined limits to selection as the availability of personnel to interpret genomics reports, the first and often emergent need for chemotherapy, access to trials or target therapy, patient refusal, and tumor heterogeneity. However, the potential of a precision medicine is far from being mentioned in an era where convergent technologies are making the movement more robust. Lot of other premises of clinical economical diagnostics as application of radiology, histopathology, and liquid biopsy apart from Cancer Genomic are becoming more recognizable in the developed world only now. The degree of synergy thus mobilized in these countries could extend to the next level of making use of intuitive electronic systems analyzing data and clinical as well as genomic databases all rolled into a single package [73,74].

Future Directions in Biomarker Research

The work done in the biomarkers field has enhanced over the last few years and it will continue enhancing unless the work done in the area is halted in the upcoming years. The expansion of frontiers of knowledge would be only possible if a new biomarker of this kind emerged and, if used properly in clinical practice, it would expand the frontiers of human experience even more. In this section, details about several of the growing trends in biomarker study and where these will be in the future are presented. With regard to preparation of biomarkers for their effective use within diagnostics and treatment monitoring, the attempts to start using different types of technologies for their analyses are also being made. As a next level in the integration of genomics, epigenomics, and transcriptomics, metabolomics and proteomics data will be added. If these endeavours become easier to achieve and less expensive, they are likely going to be incorporated in the reconnaissance stage of the research investigation. One more opportunity that has not been explored to the extent possible until present days is utilization of big data, and latest AI and machine

learning technologies in biomarker identification. One broad area therefore that may benefit from biomarker development is in the area of early detection and preventive medicine. Some of the neglected malignancies include colorectal cancer, cancer of unknown primary site, leukemia, and head and neck malignancy; more than half of the published biomarker is associated with either breast, lung or prostate malignancy alone. The most attractive novel strategies for biomarker discovery can be used as single or multiple tests simultaneously. Future biomarker hunters are reminded to be more flexible and expand the search for applications of this research in other fields. However, in our view, only a focus on the development of new biomarkers will achieve its full potential when it is based on interdisciplinary collaboration and abilities from various scientific disciplines, the opportunity to enable access to appropriate biopsy specimens or volunteers, as well as interface with those undertaking trials and assessing the cost-effectiveness of care. This is unlikely to change rapidly unless safeguarded funding and resources are injected into these agenda setting fields of research [75-77].

Personalized Biomarker Panels

Biomarker panels as Whiteside notes are the new buzz word in biomarker research and the most exciting development in biomarker analysis since cancer antigen (CA)-125 for ovarian cancer because it distinguishes patients from normal subjects, i.e., it is for diagnosis. However, such panels are also advantageous for the diagnosis and therapy of diseases because such data depend on the differences in patients in disease state. For instance, the factories of the pharmaceutical industry might conduct epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) genotyping for their patients with presumed lung cancer for research on the existence of mutations with the subsequent potential to individualize a chemical mixture. Suggestions of variation in expression or genetic markers defining the patient may yield the diagnostician and the patient a deeper understanding of the disease and augment standard clinicopathological landmarks. Furthermore, for drug development, the identification of such markers may help in discrimination of target for preclinical and or clinical trial stage and may be useful in choosing patients for the later phase clinical trials required for approval. Of course, for the application of the individual biomarkers within the scope of biomarker panels for the diagnostics and therapy of diseases, the analysis of peripheral blood as biological sample material could be interesting due to the fact that it is collected less invasively than a biopsy thus being better accepted by the patient; biopsies in turn may be less or non-representative [78-80].

Research being done in our group and in other studies is the identification of data sets that can be used to validate such face and process validity of these test designs for use in contemporary clinical environments. It is further stated that the establishment of specific, or individualised biomarker profiles, or biomarker profiles remains a challenge, for instance, with respect to costs and feasibility in the clinical arena. As the utilization of different advanced technologies including software for image analysis, different genomic sequencing techniques enhances discovery of markers or marker panels and/or their potential application it will be fairly expected to enhance. It should be understood that these technical means involve fundamentally different stages for eliminating potential batch effects such as, for example, pooling, blocking, or developing an adequate mathematical model together with the corresponding metadata about sample collection, processing, and measurement. In the future, advances in this approach may show population based individualised approach in clinical medicine, where more and more markers in bio fluids will enhance the disease prognosis and predict treatment results [81-83].

Conclusion

In the previous sections, we have outlined our position on novel biomarkers. We have shown that technological advances can lead to novel targets for these markers, and we have explored their promise. The use of plasma, serum, and urine specimens alongside tissue samples to help refine diagnosis and improve prognosis is a laudable aim, with the potential to benefit individual patients. Countless papers stress the importance of biomarkers, particularly for symmetric organs like breast and prostate, to try and enhance what is effectively a morphological diagnosis to add something more predictive. This is clearly why a supportive paymaster or industry is only too willing to support manufacturers in developing this commodity. Biochemists are continually developing new and sensitive ways to detect important biological molecules, so histopathologists are continuously involved in new markers because it is effectively our microscopy of the world of what we actually treat. This is a dialectical relationship between modern science and practice to develop new tools and tests from the working pathological armamentarium. There has been notable interest in lipids and other biological substances by the same group for a long enough period to suggest they have a guiding hand in the direction taken by members of the same firm, leading to new kits and staining procedures, thus augmenting their portfolio beyond simple hematoxylin and eosin, for example, and further enhancing the avant-garde. Hence, moreover, a grasp of currently used traditional targets and antibodies to clarify the juxtaposition of

conventional and newest markers all at the same time is a pragmatic approach, given many delegates may be practitioners and scientists in histopathology or clinical biochemistry working in more clinical sample-based environments. Collaborative working will become second nature, as multiple specialist input from molecular pathology, pathology, molecular biology, histology, immunostaining, receptor analysis, cell biology, hormone assessment, and more intertwine to provide patient-focused cards, chips, or bench-based assessments which will help truly realize personalized medicine. In conclusion, therefore, we are still at a very nascent stage in the development of truly effective, universally applicable, and personalized tumor diagnostic and prognostic markers. It will be the advancements in current techniques and truly innovative new research that will pay off in the future and eventually inform clinical practice and patient management, leading to better patient outcomes.

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